

Type	Interventions	Clinical			PLE alignment and co-development			Context and applicability		
		Clear mechanistic understanding	Sufficient moderate quality evidence of efficacy in diverse populations	Strong potential for impact	High alignment with needs of beneficiaries	PLE engagement in development or adaptation is high	Evidence of scalable implementation pathways	Applicability to low-resource settings	Evidence of cost-effectiveness or potential	Relevance during global crises
Psychological	Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT)	+	+	+	+	+	+	?	+	?
Psychological	Behavioural therapy	+	+	?	+	-	?	+	?	?
Psychological	Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT, including trauma informed)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Cognitive Remediation (CR) and cognitive enhancement therapy (CET)	+	+	?	?	-	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Cognitive therapy	+	?	?	?	-	?	?	?	?
Psychological	Common elements treatment approach (CETA)	+	+	+	?	+	?	+	+	?
Psychological	Critical Incident Stress Debriefing (CISD)	?	-	?	-	-	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Danger Ideation Reduction Therapy (DIRT)	+	+	+	?	-	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT)	+	+	?	?	-	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Exposure and response prevention therapy	+	+	+	?	+	-	?	?	?
Psychological	Eye Movement Desensitisation and Reprocessing (EMDR)	+	+	+	?	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Integrated Psychological Therapy	+	-	?	?	?	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Interactive Voice Response Therapy	+	-	?	?	?	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Interpersonal and Social Rhythm Therapy (IPSRT)	?	?	?	?	?	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Interpersonal Psychotherapy (IPT)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Life Goals Collaborative Care	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Metacognitive Therapy (MCT)	+	-	?	?	-	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Mindfulness based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT)	+	+	+	+	?	-	?	+	?
Psychological	Mindfulness-Based Interventions (MBIs)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Narrative Enhancement Cognitive Therapy (NECT)	+	+	?	?	?	-	-	?	?
Psychological	Narrative Exposure Therapy (NET)	+	+	+	?	?	+	?	+	?
Psychological	Narrative Therapy	+	+	?	?	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Problem-Solving Therapy	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Problem Management Plus (PM+)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Psychodynamic therapy	+	-	?	?	-	?	?	?	?
Psychological	Psychoeducation	+	+	?	+	?	+	+	+	?
Psychological	Psychotherapy (e.g. Morita)	+	+	?	+	?	?	?	+	?
Psychological	Reminiscence Therapy (RT)	+	+	?	?	-	?	?	?	?
Psychological	Triple chronotherapy	+	-	?	?	-	?	?	?	?
Psychological	Unguided Self-help Interventions	?	-	?	?	?	+	+	+	?
Psychosocial	Cognitive Behavioural Intervention for Trauma in Schools (CBITS)	+	?	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Psychosocial	Ecosystems Therapy	?	?	+	+	+	-	?	?	?
Psychosocial	Exercise and therapy (aerobic, yoga, resistance, Tai chi, Qi Gong)	+	+	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Psychosocial	Expression based therapy (drama, art, music, dance)	+	+	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Psychosocial	Family Therapy, including risk reduction family therapy, family-focused therapy	+	+	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Psychosocial	Functional remediation	+	+	?	?	?	-	?	?	?
Psychosocial	Horticultural Therapy	?	?	?	?	?	-	?	?	?
Psychosocial	Nutrition weight loss, Exercise, and Wellness treatment (NEW Tx)	+	?	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Psychosocial	Skills based therapy (parent training, problem solving)	+	?	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Psychosocial	Social Cognitive Interaction Training (SCIT)	+	?	?	?	?	?	+	?	?
Psychosocial	Social Skills Training Programmes (SSP)	+	+	?	+	?	?	?	+	+
Psychosocial	Traditional Chinese practice and acupoint Massage	?	?	?	?	?	-	?	?	?
Psychosocial	Momentum (co-created local programme)	+	?	?	+	?	?	?	?	?
Psychosocial	Safe Space	+	?	?	?	?	?	+	?	?
Psychosocial	Community based sociotherapy	+	?	?	?	?	-	?	?	?
Psychosocial	Resilience-Oriented Group Therapy: A Strengths-based & Trauma-informed Modular Treatment for Emotion Regulation, Behavioral Self-Management & Identity Development	+	?	?	?	+	-	+	+	?
Psychosocial	Lacaweb - combined healing, mind-body, self-help and other therapies - described as movement	?	?	?	+	?	?	+	?	?
Psychosocial	Friendship Bench	+	?	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Psychosocial	Solution-Focused Brief Therapy	+	?	?	+	+	+	+	?	?
Social	Assertive Community Treatment	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Social	Social skill interventions (e.g. Shamiri intervention and other school focused intervention building empowerment)	+	?	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Social	Social support and connections interventions	+	+	+	+	?	?	+	?	+
Social	Supported employment and workplace related programmes	+	+	+	+	?	?	?	?	+
Social	Let's work together programme	?	?	?	+	?	?	+	?	+
Social	Legal interventions expanding de facto access to health services	+	+	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Social	Housing first (or similar interventions)	+	+	+	+	?	?	?	?	+
Social	Cash transfers	?	+	+	+	?	?	+	?	+
Social	Food security interventions	?	+	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Social	Violence and security focused interventions	?	?	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Social	Clubhouse model	+	+	+	+	?	?	+	+	+
Social	Atmiyata	+	?	?	+	+	+	?	?	+
Social	WHO Quality Rights modules and framing	?	?	?	+	+	-	+	?	+

+ High potential
 - Low potential
 ? Unclear potential